

Photochemistry of Complex Ions. $\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2^-$ and $\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_3\text{Cl}^+$ Ions

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The complex ions $\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2^-$ and $\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_3\text{Cl}^+$ were studied so as to complete the photochemical picture for the family of chloroammines. Irradiation of $\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2^-$ with yellow light leads to chloride aquation with the formation of *cis*- and *trans*- $\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}_2$, in the ratio 2 : 1. The quantum yield for production of the *cis*-isomer is 0.140. The quantum yield and the isomer ratio are nearly independent of the wavelength of irradiating light and of temperature. The second complex, $\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_3\text{Cl}^+$ undergoes both ammonia and chloride aquation on irradiation in the near ultraviolet. The photochemical reaction modes of both chloroamine complexes differ from the thermal reaction modes.

THE nature of bonding in coordination compounds has been of interest for a long time. Thermal reaction studies, spectroscopy and, recently, photochemical investigations are the various methods used to understand the bonding and reactivity of these compounds.¹ The photochemistry of chromium(III) and cobalt(III) complexes has been studied in detail and certain generalities were observed regarding the excited state processes.² Platinum(II) complexes are well known examples of square planar geometry and the thermal reactions of these complexes have been studied extensively.³ Substitution reactions in the dark seem to follow an associative type mechanism involving a transition state with pentacoordination. Spectroscopic details of the electronic excited states are known to some extent⁴. The chloroamine complexes of platinum (II) are well characterized in their thermal reactions and the absorption spectra of these complexes have been investigated. These details help to a great extent in the study of excited states. The photochemistry of *cis*- and *trans*- $\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2$ and PtCl_2^{2-} has been investigated⁵. These complexes undergo photolysis substituting water for chloride ligands similar to the thermal reaction. This paper gives an account of the photochemistry of $\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2^-$ and $\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_3\text{Cl}^+$ ions. $\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2^-$ ion undergoes the following thermal reactions³

$\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_3\text{Cl}^+$ ion undergoes thermal aquation,

Spectroscopic details^{7,8} of these complexes are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SPECTRAL DETAILS OF $\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2^-$ and $\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_3\text{Cl}^+$ IONS

Complex	λ max, nm	ϵ max $\text{m}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$	Transition
$\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2^-$	300	68	$^1A_1 \rightarrow ^1B_1$
	346	115	$^1A_1 \rightarrow ^1A_2$
	415	22	$^1A_1 \rightarrow ^3A_2$ or $^1A_1 \rightarrow ^3B_1$
$\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_3\text{Cl}^+$	255	110	$^1A_1 \rightarrow ^1B_1$
	278	70	$^1A_1 \rightarrow ^1A_2$
	323	36	$^1A_1 \rightarrow ^3A_2$ or $^1A_1 \rightarrow ^3B_1$

Experimental

Potassiumtrichloroammineplatinate(II) was prepared by the procedure given by Elleman et al.¹⁰. Chlorotriammineplatinum(II) was prepared following the procedure of Chatt et al.¹⁰. Complexes were recrystallized from water and the purity was checked by comparing the UV-visible spectra with those in the literature^{9,9}. Spectra of our samples agreed to well within 5% of the reported extinction coefficients.

Irradiations were carried out using a General Electric AH 6 high pressure mercury lamp and with an Hanovia medium pressure mercury A 673 A lamp. Irradiation set up was similar to that described earlier.¹¹ Specific bands of the compounds were irradiated using a beam of narrow band width which was obtained using Bausch and Lomb interference filters and corning glass filters. The incident light intensity was measured using ferrioxalate actinometry.¹² Absorption spectra were scanned using a Cary 14 spectrophotometer. Kinetic studies were done in a DU Beckmann spectrophotometer. The cell compartment was thermostated to within $\pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$. Concentrations of the irradiated solutions were such that more than 95% of the incident light was absorbed. In cases where it was not so, suitable corrections were made in the calculation of quantum yield.

Estimation of cis- and trans- isomers of $Pt(NH_3)(H_2O)Cl_2$ produced during the photolysis of $KPt(NH_3)Cl_3$: To the irradiated solution of $Pt(NH_3)Cl_3$ ion, potassium chloride solution was added in excess, by maintaining the temperature of the solutions at $25 \pm 0.2^\circ C$. Back anation reaction was followed by noting the optical density change at 345 nm. The optical density of the solution did not change after 5 or 6 hours. The optical density at infinite time was measured after 6 hours. A plot of $\log [(0.D)_\infty - (0.D)_t]$ Vs time is shown in Figure 1. Determination of the slope indicates that the linear portion corresponds to the anation of *trans*- $Pt(NH_3)(H_2O)Cl_2$ to give $Pt(NH_3)Cl_3$ ion. That portion of the curve corresponding to the anation of *cis*- $Pt(NH_3)(H_2O)Cl_2$ was resolved as shown. The intercepts are proportional to the concentrations of the two isomers produced photochemically. Knowing the extinction coefficients of *cis*- and *trans*- $Pt(NH_3)(H_2O)Cl_2$ at 345 nm, the concentration of the photolysis products was determined.

Figure 1. Anation of photolysed $Pt(NH_3)Cl_3$ ion

Results

Photolysis of $Pt(NH_3)Cl_3$ ion: 1.5 mM solution of $Pt(NH_3)Cl_3$ ion on irradiation in the region 310-390 nm undergoes decomposition. Spectral changes observed for different irradiation periods along with the spectrum of the unirradiated solution is shown in Figure 2. Addition of excess chloride to the irradiated solution regenerates the spectrum of unirradiated solution. Ammonia release would have produced the trichloroaquoplatinate(II) ion which in the presence of chloride forms tetrachloroplatinate(II). Spectra of $PtCl_4^{2-}$ and $Pt(NH_3)Cl_3$ are so that one per cent

decomposition of $Pt(NH_3)Cl_3$ to give rise to ammonia could be detected by means of spectral changes.

Figure 2. Photolysis of $Pt(NH_3)Cl_3$ ion. A-unirradiated solution, B, C and D corresponds to irradiation for 5, 10 and 15 min.

When the photodecomposition of the complex was limited to less than 10%, assuming no secondary photolysis has occurred, photolysis of $Pt(NH_3)Cl_3$ ion can be described as

From the back anation studies, the amount of *cis*- and *trans*-isomers formed during the photolysis has been calculated. Results of the quantum yield dependence on wavelength of irradiation is shown in Table 2. The temperature of the irradiated solutions was varied and

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF QUANTUM YIELD WITH THE WAVELENGTH OF IRRADIATION FOR THE PHOTOAQUATION OF $Pt(NH_3)Cl_3$ ION

[complex] = $1.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ Irradiation temperature $25^\circ C$ $[Cl^-] = 0.071 M$

Time min.	[cis] $10^4 M$	[trans] $10^4 M$	[cis] / [trans]	ϕ	ϕ_{cis}	ϕ_{trans}
2 ^a	0.72	0.346	2.146	0.189	0.128	0.061
3 ^a	1.590	0.416	3.82	0.236	0.180	0.050
5 ^a	1.680	0.816	2.06	0.193	0.130	0.063
3 ^b	0.794	0.415	1.910	0.278	0.182	0.096
4 ^b	0.978	0.520	1.880	0.258	0.168	0.090
6 ^b	1.360	0.606	2.24	0.276	0.190	0.056

^a Filters UG11+CS-052 λ_{max} of irradiation = 350 nm
^b Filters BL-410+CS-052 λ_{max} of irradiation = 410 nm

the variation of quantum yield with irradiation temperature is shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3—QUANTUM YIELD DEPENDENCE ON THE IRRADIATION TEMPERATURE FOR PHOTOAQUATION OF $Pt(NH_3)_3Cl_2^+$ ION

Time min.	[cis] $\times 10^4 M$	[trans] $\times 10^4 M$	$\frac{[cis]}{[trans]}$	ϕ	ϕ_{cis}	ϕ_{trans}
3 _b	0.668	0.338	1.90	0.207	0.135	0.072
4 _b	0.820	0.661	1.24	0.227	0.126	0.101
5 _b	1.34	0.690	1.94	0.180	0.115	0.062
4 _c	0	0.670	1.31	0.237	0.135	0.102
5 _c	1.12	0.715	1.52	0.225	0.136	0.089

^a Filter UG11 + CS-052 Irradiation $\lambda_{max} = 350$ nm
[complex] = $1.5 \times 10^{-5} M$, $[Cl^-] = 0.071 M$

^b $30 \pm 0.2^\circ C$

^c $20 \pm 0.2^\circ C$

Photolysis of $Pt(NH_3)_3Cl^+$ ion: Irradiation of an aqueous solution of $Pt(NH_3)_3Cl^+$ produces the spectral changes indicated in Figure 3. Added excess chloride did not reproduce the spectrum of unirradiated solution from which it was concluded that both ammonia and chloride release take place on irradiation. Since the spectra of the expected products do not differ greatly from that of the starting material, the photoreaction could not be analysed spectrophotometrically. Several chromatographic procedures were tried in order to identify the products. The complex $Pt(NH_3)_3Cl^+$ and ammonium ion have the same charge and ion-exchange chromatography could not separate ammonium ion alone.

Figure 3. Photolysis of $Pt(NH_3)_3Cl^+$ ion.
A—unirradiated solution.
B—irradiated solution.

Discussion

The series of chloroammine complexes of platinum(II), $Pt(NH_3)_{4-n}Cl_n^{2-n}$ ($n=0$ to 4) aquates thermally to release chloride ligand. Ammonia is not released in the thermal reaction in any one of these complexes. With the investigations reported here, the photochemistry of all complexes in this series has been looked at. $Pt(NH_3)_4^{2+}$ ion does not appear to be photosensitive. $Pt(NH_3)_3Cl^+$ releases chloride and probably ammonia with very low quantum yield (ϕ 0.01). Ammonia release from this complex is inferred indirectly as the irradiated solution in the presence of excess chloride does not produce quantitatively $Pt(NH_3)_3Cl^+$ ion. Photoisomerization has not been shown to occur either with *cis*- $Pt(NH_3)_2Cl_2$ or *trans*- $Pt(NH_3)_2Cl_2$. No redox process occurs in these complexes due to irradiation.

In this series of chloroammine complexes, the quantum yield for the chloride release varies from 0.3 to 0.03 on irradiating lower energy ligand field bands. For $PtCl_4^{2-}$ ion, the quantum yield for chloride release is ~ 0.2 . It is suggested^{6b} that the photoreaction occurs from a thermally equilibrated electronic excited state which has a distorted tetrahedral geometry. It is not clear whether a 'hot' ground state is also an additional path for the release of chloride ion. Indeed a distorted excited state geometry was proposed for $PtCl_4^{2-}$ ion from single crystal and polarized absorption spectral studies.^{1,8} As far as the photochemistry of $Pt(NH_3)_3Cl^+$ ion is concerned, the ratio of *cis*- to *trans*- isomer of $Pt(NH_3)_2(H_2O)Cl_2$ formed is about 2. From the rate constants for the thermal reactions, the ratio of *cis*- to *trans*- $Pt(NH_3)_2(H_2O)Cl_2$ produced should have been around 10 to 1 if the photoreaction is an accelerated form of the thermal reaction. The photochemical reaction thus follows an entirely different path. The quantum yield for chloride release in *cis*- $Pt(NH_3)_2Cl_2$ on photolysis varies from 0.25 to 0.46 whereas in *trans*- $Pt(NH_3)_2Cl_2$ it is 0.01. In all these cases ammonia release was not observed. It is interesting to apply Adamson's rules^{1,4} for the photolysis of chromium(III) complexes to platinum(II) complexes. For *cis*- $Pt(NH_3)_2Cl_2$, the first rule does not apply since both axes are equivalent. The second rule predicts the release of ammonia which was not observed. For *trans*- $Pt(NH_3)_2Cl_2$, the labilised axis is the one which is predicted by the first rule. The second rule does not apply to this complex. In the case of $Pt(NH_3)_3Cl^+$, the labilised axis is the one with the smaller crystal field strength. Since the labilised axis contains only chloridic ligands, the second rule does not apply. However, the applicability of the photolysis rules for platinum(II) complexes should be closely examined with the investigation of more complexes.

Sensitization studies have helped in understanding the nature of reactive electronic excited states in another platinum(II) complex, $Pt(C_2H_4)Cl_3^{1,6}$. A number of sensitization studies have been reported for platinum(II) complexes^{7,6,17} which should be extended to this series of complexes also in order to have a better understanding of their photochemistry.

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